

1 **A high-throughput, microplate reader-based method to monitor *in vitro* HIV latency reversal in**
2 **the absence of flow cytometry**

3
4 Chantal Emade Nkwelle^{a,b,f}, Unique Stephens^{c,f}, Kimberly Liang^c, Joel Cassel^c, Joseph M. Salvino
5 ^c, Luis J. Montaner^c, Roland N. Ndip^a, Seraphine N. Esemu^a, Fidele Ntie-Kang^{b,d,e,*}, and Ian Tietjen

6 ^{c,*}

7
8 ^a, Department of Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Science, University of Buea, Buea,
9 Cameroon

10 ^b, Center for Drug Discovery, University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon

11 ^c, The Wistar Institute of Anatomy and Biology, Philadelphia, PA, USA

12 ^d, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon

13 ^e, Institute of Pharmacy, Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Halle (Saale), Germany.

14 ^f, These authors contributed equally.

15
16 **Correspondence:** Fidele Ntie-Kang [Center for Drug Discovery, Faculty of Science, P.O. Box 63,
17 University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon] and Ian Tietjen [The Wistar Institute, 3601 Spruce Street,
18 Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA]

19 Tel: +237 673872475 (F.N.K.); +1 215-898-3938 (I.T.)

20 Email: fidele.ntie-kang@ubuea.com (F.N.K.) ; itietjen@wistar.org (I.T.)

21 **Summary**

22 J-Lat cells are derivatives of the Jurkat CD4+ T cell line that contain a non-infectious,
23 inducible HIV provirus with a GFP tag. While these cells have substantially advanced our
24 understanding of HIV latency, their use by many laboratories in low and middle-income countries is
25 restricted by limited access to flow cytometry. To overcome this barrier, we describe a modified J-
26 Lat assay using a standard microplate reader that detects HIV-GFP expression following treatment
27 with latency-reversing agents (LRAs). We show that HIV reactivation by control LRAs like prostratin
28 and romidepsin is readily detected with dose dependence and with significant correlation and
29 sensitivity to standard flow cytometry. For example, 10 μM prostratin induced a 20.1 ± 3.3 -fold
30 increase in GFP fluorescence in the microplate reader assay, which corresponded to $64.2 \pm 5.0\%$
31 GFP-positive cells detected by flow cytometry. Similarly, 0.3 μM prostratin induced a 1.7 ± 1.2 -fold
32 increase compared to $8.7 \pm 5.7\%$ GFP-positive cells detected. Using this method, we screen 79
33 epigenetic modifiers and identify CUDC-101, molibresib, and quisinostat as novel LRAs. This
34 microplate reader-based method offers accessibility to researchers in resource-limited regions to
35 work with J-Lat cells and more actively participate in global HIV cure research efforts.

36

37 **Keywords**

38 HIV latency, J-Lat cell line, latency-reversing agents, microplate reader, resource-limited
39 laboratories

40

41 **Highlights**

- 42 • J-Lat T-cell lines are important to HIV cure research but require flow cytometry
- 43 • We describe a method to work with J-Lat cells using a standard microplate reader
- 44 • This assay can detect control LRAs similar to flow cytometry and discover new LRAs

45 • This assay allows low-resourced laboratories to contribute to HIV cure research

46

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Current antiretroviral therapy (ART) does not eliminate latent HIV proviruses present in CD4+
49 T-cells that can reactivate at any time to produce infectious virus. As a result, people living with HIV
50 must maintain an ART regimen for life. Successfully identifying and eliminating these latent HIV
51 reservoirs within CD4+ T-cells would mark a major milestone toward achieving ART-free HIV
52 remission or an HIV cure. A common approach in early-stage HIV cure-based drug discovery is to
53 identify small molecules that can reactive HIV expression from latently infected cells as part of larger
54 efforts to eliminate these cells through cell death or immune system induction. This approach,
55 frequently termed “shock-and-kill” or “kick-and-kill,” has identified hundreds of latency-reversing
56 agents (LRAs) that reactivate virus expression in HIV-infected primary cells, animal models of latent
57 HIV infection, and/or in people living with HIV (Board et al., 2022; Mbonye and Karn, 2024). However,
58 as no LRA-based strategy has demonstrated consistent reduction of HIV reservoirs in humans,
59 optimizing existing LRAs as well as discovery of new LRAs remain critical.

60 Discovery and validation of new LRAs frequently begin with the use of HIV reservoir-based
61 cell lines which afford high-throughput and low-cost screening of chemical libraries. Among the
62 available cell lines are J-Lat cells, which are derived from Jurkat CD4+ T-cells but contain a latent
63 HIV provirus where the viral *env* and *nef* genes are replaced with a GFP reporter (Jordan et al., 2003).
64 As a result, cells produce GFP upon HIV latency reversal and virus expression, which is readily
65 monitored by flow cytometry. Using this approach, numerous LRAs and other regulators of virus
66 transcription have been discovered, significantly advancing our understandings of HIV latency as
67 well as development of therapeutic leads to eventually achieve ART-free HIV remission or cure (e.g.,
68 Abdel-Mohsen et al., 2016; Abner et al., 2018; Hashemi et al., 2018; Richard et al., 2018; Acchioni et
69 al., 2019; Matsuda et al., 2019; Hseih et al., 2023; Nichols Doyle et al., 2023).

70 One attractive characteristic of J-Lat cell lines, in addition to their open availability, is that
71 they can produce largely intact but non-infectious virus, which makes them suitable for use by both
72 early-stage trainees and laboratories which lack sufficient biosafety containment for culturing
73 infectious HIV. This may be particularly appealing to many low-resource laboratories in low and
74 middle-income countries like those in Sub-Saharan Africa, which continues to be disproportionately
75 affected by the HIV pandemic (van Schalkwyk et al., 2024) and where supporting more locally based
76 HIV cure research is a high priority. However, while J-Lat cells can be readily cultured in a laboratory
77 with a biosafety cabinet and cell culture incubator, detection of latency reversal in these cells
78 remains challenging for many low-resource labs as they frequently lack access to costly flow
79 cytometry equipment and software and the ongoing expertise needed to use and maintain them. As
80 a result, variations of standard J-Lat-based assays are needed to make this important research tool
81 more available to those in resource-limited laboratories.

82 Toward addressing this barrier, we describe here a modified J-Lat based assay which uses a
83 standard microplate reader to detect latency reversal from both J-Lat 10.6 cells, which readily
84 respond to control LRAs by high GFP expression in most cells, as well as J-Lat 6.3 cells, which induce
85 low-level GFP following latency reversal. We show here that comparable and reproducible dose-
86 dependent latency reversal due to control LRAs is detected by microplate reader with similar
87 sensitivity to flow cytometry methods. We also demonstrate proof-of-concept of novel LRA
88 discovery by screening a library of 79 chemical epigenetic modifiers to identify three compounds not
89 previously reported to function as LRAs. This alternative assay approach, which can substitute for
90 flow cytometry, offers improved accessibility to researchers in resource-limited regions to discover
91 and characterize novel LRAs and HIV latency as well as more actively participate in global HIV cure
92 efforts.

93

94 **2. Materials and Methods**

95 *2.1. Cells and reagents*

96 J-Lat T cell clones 10.6 and 6.3 were obtained from the NIH AIDS Reagent Program, Division
97 of AIDS, NIAID, NIH (contributed by Dr. Eric Verdin; Jordan et al., 2003). Cells were cultured in R10+
98 medium [RPMI 1640 with HEPES and L-glutamine (Corning Life Sciences, Corning, NY, USA), 10%
99 heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), and 100
100 units/mL of penicillin plus 100 µg/mL streptomycin (Gibco)] in a humidified incubator at 37 °C and
101 5% CO₂. Cells were cultured to a cell density of 1 – 2 million cells/mL before use and subcultured to
102 a concentration of 10⁵ cells/mL every 2 – 3 days. Excess cells were stored in cryopreservation vials
103 (Cryotube vials, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at a concentration of 2 * 10⁶ cells/mL in R10+
104 supplemented with 40% FBS and 10% DMSO, slow-frozen in a Mr. Frosty cryofreezing container
105 containing isopropanol (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 24 hours at -80 °C, and stored long-term at -
106 120 °C or lower. Cultured cells were maintained for a maximum of 30 passages, after which a frozen
107 vial of cells was rapid-thawed and cultured using standard cell culture thawing techniques.

108 Control LRAs prostratin and romidepsin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO,
109 USA) and MedChemExpress (Monmouth Junction, NJ, USA), respectively. Epigenetic inhibitors were
110 obtained from the SelleckChem Anti-Cancer Library (Selleck Chemicals, Houston, TX, USA). Control
111 LRAs and test agents were diluted in DMSO and stored at -20 °C until use.

112

113 *2.2. LRA screening*

114 Test agents, control LRAs, and vehicle controls were diluted in PBS (Corning Life Sciences,
115 Corning, NY, USA) and aliquoted in duplicate into single wells of sterile V-bottom or U-bottom 96-
116 well plates (Corning) in 2 µL volumes each reflecting 100X final concentrations. Cell concentrations
117 for J-Lat cell culture were determined using a standard hemocytometer. Cultures were then

118 centrifuged at 500 g for 5 minutes, aspirated of culture medium, and resuspended in fresh,
119 prewarmed R10+ to a concentration of 5×10^6 cells/mL unless otherwise specified. 200 μ L aliquots
120 of resuspended cells were then distributed into wells. If cell viability using resazurin was planned,
121 an additional two wells containing only R10+ were also prepared on each plate. Cells were then
122 placed in a humidified incubator at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ for 24 \pm 4 hours.

123 If flow cytometry was planned, cells were gently resuspended following incubation, and 20
124 μ L of each cell culture was transferred to a fresh 96-well plate. Cells were then supplemented with
125 180 μ L of pre-warmed R10+ medium and optionally incubated for up to 4 additional hours before
126 analysis by flow cytometry. Flow cytometry was performed using a FACSCelesta Flow Cytometer (BD
127 Bioscience, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA), where gating of live cells and percent HIV latency for each well
128 were obtained as described previously (Richard et al., 2018). Flow cytometry data were analyzed
129 using FlowJo v.10.10.0 software (FlowJo LLC, Ashland, OR, USA).

130 For microplate reading, following incubation, cell culture plates were spun at 500 g for 5
131 minutes, flicked over a waste receptacle in a rapid, smooth motion to discard supernatant, lightly
132 pat-dried against clean paper towels, and resuspended in 200 μ L of pre-warmed PBS. Cells were
133 washed an additional three times in pre-warmed PBS using these steps. After the final wash, cells
134 were resuspended in 200 μ L PBS and transferred to a white/opaque 96-well flat bottom plate
135 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). GFP fluorescence was then measured using a ClarioStar plate reader
136 (BMG Labtech, Cary, NC, USA).

137 If measurement of cell viability was planned, 20 μ L of a 0.2 mg/mL stock of resazurin (Sigma-
138 Aldrich) was subsequently added to each well, and cells were incubated in the white/opaque plate
139 (in PBS) with a lid at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ for an additional 2 to 4 hours. Cells were then re-read in the
140 microplate reader for absorbance at 570 nm or fluorescence set as close as possible to 550 nm

141 excitation and 590 nm emission. Background signal was then subtracted from all wells based on the
142 signal from control wells containing R10+ medium and resazurin but no cells.

143

144 **3. Results and Discussion**

145 *3.1. Overview of microplate reader-based LRA screening method*

146 **Figure 1** presents an overview of the microplate reader-based method to measure HIV
147 latency reversal from J-Lat cells *in vitro*. Briefly, test agents, LRA controls, and vehicle controls like
148 DMSO are diluted in PBS to working concentrations that are 100-fold more concentrated than final
149 concentrations. 2 μ L of each test agent or control is then aliquoted in duplicate into single wells of
150 96-well V or U-bottom cell culture plates, with the expectation that subsequent addition of J-Lat cells
151 will dilute the concentrations of test agents and controls by 100-fold to desired working
152 concentrations. This approach is recommended for LRA stocks that are dissolved in DMSO, as we
153 find that DMSO working concentrations greater than 0.6% can affect background GFP expression
154 and/or J-Lat T-cell viability. Each 96-well plate also contains an untreated cell control, a vehicle-only
155 control (e.g., 0.1% DMSO final concentration), and a positive control like prostratin (e.g., 10 μ M final
156 concentration). If cell viability measures are desired, an additional two cells containing only medium
157 are added to each plate. Control conditions are also performed in duplicate. J-Lat cells are then
158 counted, centrifuged at 500 g for 5 minutes at room temperature, and resuspended in fresh media
159 to a concentration of up to 5 million cells/mL. 200 μ L of cells are then aliquoted into each well and
160 incubated for 24 hours (\pm 4 hours) in a humidified incubator at 37 $^{\circ}$ C with 5% CO₂.

161 Following incubation, cell culture plates are centrifuged at 500 g for 5 minutes at room
162 temperature and washed with PBS a total of three times. Cells are then resuspended once more in
163 200 μ L PBS and transferred to white 96-well plates. Cells are then immediately read in a 96-well
164 microplate reader that can detect GFP fluorescence. Data are presented as the fold-change of GFP

165 fluorescence relative to the average GFP fluorescence of untreated or vehicle-treated cells (e.g.,
166 0.1% DMSO).

167 After reading GFP, cells can be optionally measured for cell viability, for example with a final
168 concentration of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ resazurin (alamar blue) and further incubation in a humidified incubator at
169 37 °C with 5% CO_2 for 4 hours. Cells are then re-read in the microplate reader for absorbance at 570
170 nm or fluorescence set as close as possible to 550 nm excitation and 590 nm emission. For data
171 analysis, the background signal of medium-only wells is then subtracted from all wells, and resulting
172 data are then normalized to the average intensities of untreated or vehicle-treated cells.

173

174 *3.2. Robust and quantitative GFP fluorescence in J-Lat 10.6 cells is detected by microplate reader-*
175 *based method and correlates with fluorescence detected by flow cytometry*

176 Using this approach, we assessed the ability of the microplate reader-based method to
177 detect HIV reactivation induced by control LRAs in J-Lat 10.6 cells. These LRAs included prostratin,
178 which reverses HIV latency through activating protein kinase C signaling, and romidepsin, which acts
179 via inhibition of histone deacetylases (HDACs) (Andersen et al., 2018). To measure dependence of
180 cell concentration on GFP signals obtained by microplate reader, we treated cells at three different
181 concentrations including 1, 2.5, and 5×10^6 cells/mL (corresponding respectively to 2×10^5 , 5×10^5 ,
182 and 10^6 cells/well in 200 μL final volume) with LRAs. From this experiment, we detected robust GFP
183 expression at all cell concentrations for both LRAs with dose dependence (**Figures 2A-C**). We also
184 observed that higher cell concentrations induced more detectable GFP signal from both LRAs. For
185 example, we observed a 12.3 ± 1.4 -fold increase in GFP fluorescence (mean \pm s.e.m.) in cells treated
186 with 10 μM prostratin, relative to cells treated with 0.1% DMSO vehicle control, when cultured at 10^6
187 cells/mL (**Figure 2A**), while cells cultured at 2.5 and 5×10^6 cells/mL respectively exhibited 21.3 ± 2.6
188 and 20.1 ± 3.3 -fold increases in GFP, relative to 0.1% DMSO-treated cells (**Figures 2B-C**). In contrast,

189 in cells cultured at 10^6 cells/mL, we observed only a 5.8 ± 0.5 -fold increase in GFP fluorescence from
190 cells treated with $0.3 \mu\text{M}$ romidepsin, although this concentration of romidepsin did induce more
191 GFP fluorescence in cells cultured at 2.5 and 5×10^6 cells/mL (respectively 7.1 ± 0.7 and 9.3 ± 1.5 -
192 fold increases in fluorescence, respectively; **Figures 2A-C**). However, when these cells were
193 subsequently assessed for cell viability following staining with resazurin, we observed, as expected,
194 that while prostratin induced a maximum of $47.2 \pm 6.1\%$ loss in viability at $30 \mu\text{M}$, substantial cell
195 death was observed in romidepsin-treated cells, with calculated half-maximal cytotoxic
196 concentrations ($\text{CC}_{50\text{s}}$) of $0.037 \mu\text{M}$ or lower (**Figures 2D-F**). This suggests that the reduced
197 romidepsin-dependent signal observed relative to prostratin-dependent fluorescence might be
198 attributable to cytotoxicity.

199 To compare this microplate reader-based assay with standard methods, we removed $20 \mu\text{L}$
200 of each cell culture following the 24-hour incubation above and before plate spinning and PBS
201 washes. These cells were then added to $180 \mu\text{L}$ of fresh media and processed directly by flow
202 cytometry (**Figure 1**). Removal of these cells did not obviously affect the magnitude of GFP detection
203 by microplate (data not shown). As shown in **Figures 2G-I**, we observed that GFP expression in live
204 gated, LRA-treated cells was largely biphasic, where the majority of GFP-expressing cells exhibit
205 fluorescence that was ~ 100 -fold higher than the background signal in GFP-negative cells. As a result,
206 we elected in this study to measure GFP expression in flow cytometry experiments based on
207 percent GFP-positive cells (e.g., as opposed to measuring mean fluorescence intensity).

208 As shown in **Figures 2J-L**, similar levels of GFP fluorescence in live-gated cells were observed
209 across all cell concentrations, indicating no major effects on latency reversal due to cell
210 concentration, although somewhat fewer GFP-positive cells were seen at some concentrations of
211 prostratin in cells cultured at 5×10^6 cells/mL (**Figure 2L**). For example, at $3 \mu\text{M}$ prostratin we
212 observed 54.7 ± 3.6 and $53.8 \pm 4.7\%$ GFP-positive cells from the live cell gates of cells cultured at 1

213 and 2.5×10^6 cells/mL, respectively, but only $34.1 \pm 1.5\%$ GFP-positive cells in the live cell gates from
214 cells cultured at 5×10^6 cells/mL, indicating minor but consistent dampening of GFP expression
215 induced by control LRAs in cells cultured at high concentrations. In contrast, GFP signals induced
216 by romidepsin were robust across all samples where, for example, at $0.3 \mu\text{M}$ romidepsin, we
217 observed 68.1 ± 7.0 , 65.8 ± 7.8 , and $61.4 \pm 11.6\%$ GFP-positive cells from the live cell gates of cells
218 cultured at 1 and 2.5, and 5×10^6 cells/mL, respectively (**Figures 2J-L**). Notably, unlike observations
219 from the microplate reader, latency reversal induced by romidepsin also approximated that of
220 prostratin in flow cytometry studies, which reflects standard flow cytometry data analysis where only
221 the subset of live cells, based on characteristic forward and side scatter parameters, are gated and
222 analyzed.

223 To determine the extent to which HIV latency reversal detected by microplate reader (as
224 measured by fold-change in GFP expression relative to no-drug control) correlated to signals
225 detected by flow cytometry (as measured by percent GFP-positive, live-gated cells), we obtained the
226 total data points of J-Lat 10.6 cells treated with prostratin and romidepsin at all concentrations
227 across four independent experiments and graphed microplate reader data as a function of flow
228 cytometry data (**Figure 3**). By performing simple linear regression analysis, we found that
229 correlations between microplate reader and flow cytometry data improved in proportion to the
230 concentration of J-Lat 10.6 cells in cell culture (**Figure 3A-C**). For example, while J-Lat 10.6 cells
231 cultured at 1 million cells/mL exhibited an r^2 value 0.32 between the respective microplate reader
232 and flow cytometry data, we observed more correlation between these readings of the same
233 experiments when J-Lat 10.6 cells were cultured at 2.5 million cells/mL ($r^2 = 0.55$) and 5 million
234 cells/mL ($r^2 = 0.65$). Within the subset of data points where cells were treated with only one control
235 LRA in J-Lat cells cultured at 5 million cells/mL, we also observed good correlation of the two

236 detection methods in cells treated with prostratin ($r^2 = 0.81$) and romidepsin ($r^2 = 0.79$) (**Figure 3D-**
237 **E**). All correlations were statistically significant by linear regression ($p < 0.001$).

238 Taken together, these results indicate that the microplate reader-based method detects HIV
239 latency reversal in J-Lat cells by LRAs with dose dependence that recapitulates results obtained by
240 standard flow cytometry methods. Based on these results, we performed subsequent experiments
241 using J-Lat cells at a concentration of $5 * 10^6$ cells/mL, or 10^6 cells/well in 200 μ L.

242

243 *3.3. Reduced but reproducible GFP fluorescence in J-Lat 6.3 cells is detected by microplate reader-* 244 *based method*

245 To determine whether the microplate reader-based method of detecting HIV latency reversal
246 could be expanded to other J-Lat cell lines, we next investigated whether we could detect GFP
247 expression induced by prostratin or romidepsin in J-Lat 6.3 cells. These cells represent another J-Lat
248 cell clone where the HIV provirus is integrated at a different genomic location and where fewer GFP-
249 positive cells are induced by LRAs (Fernandez and Zeichner, 2010). However, unlike J-Lat 10.6 cells,
250 where GFP fluorescence of 10 to 20-fold over untreated control cells was routinely detected
251 following romidepsin or prostratin treatment (**Figure 2C**), we observed no more than a 2.2 ± 0.4 -fold
252 increase (mean \pm s.e.m.) in fluorescence in the presence of 0.3 μ M romidepsin (**Figure 4A**).
253 Consistent with the reduced induction of virus expression by LRAs in this cell model, we also
254 detected fewer GFP-positive cells by flow cytometry, for example following treatment with 10 μ M
255 prostratin (average $11.7 \pm 5.5\%$ GFP-positive cells) or 0.3 μ M romidepsin (average $13.3 \pm 6.2\%$ GFP-
256 positive cells; **Figure 4B**). While dose-response curves for both prostratin and romidepsin were
257 detected in J-Lat 6.3 cells using both methods, more variability between three independent
258 experiments for each assay was observed. Furthermore, when graphing microplate reader and flow
259 cytometry datapoints for two experiments where both assays were performed, a lower correlation

260 was observed between the two assays ($r^2 = 0.37$; **Figure 4C**), although this correlation remained
261 significant ($p = 0.005$). Finally, while correlations for the subset of datapoints from prostratin
262 treatment had good correlation ($r^2 = 0.67$; $p = 0.004$), no correlation was observed in romidepsin-
263 treated samples ($r^2 = 0.11$; $p = 0.36$), possibly due to the loss of cell viability at high concentrations
264 of romidepsin (**Figure 4D**). These results suggest that the microplate reader-based method is
265 capable of detecting HIV latency reversal by LRAs with dose-dependence in J-Lat 6.3 cells but with
266 more variability.

267

268 *3.4. Discovery of novel LRAs in J-Lat 10.6 cells using microplate reader-based method*

269 To determine whether the microplate reader-based method could be used to identify novel
270 LRAs, we assembled a library of 79 epigenetic modifiers (**Table 1**) and screened them in duplicate at
271 10 μ M in J-Lat 10.6 cells using the procedures above. We also assessed the same cells in parallel by
272 flow cytometry, where good correlation of data from both microplate reader and flow cytometry was
273 maintained ($r^2 = 0.67$, $p < 0.001$; **Figure 5A**). However, a few outliers were detected; for example,
274 bromosporine resulted in a 78.5 ± 6.8 -fold increase in GFP fluorescence by microplate reader but
275 only $35.2 \pm 2.3\%$ GFP-positive cells by flow cytometry. Further, CUDC-101 treatment caused an 18.7
276 ± 0.8 -fold increase in GFP fluorescence by microplate reader but $49.4 \pm 27.4\%$ GFP-positive cells by
277 flow cytometry, although this likely reflects a technical discrepancy in a single replicate in flow
278 cytometry. However, both compounds would clearly constitute screening “hits” assuming a
279 conservative “hit” threshold of 15-fold increase in GFP by microplate reader.

280 When focusing exclusively on the microplate reader-based data, we found that prostratin
281 induced a 41.7 ± 0.6 -fold (mean \pm SD) increased GFP signal relative to untreated cells, while 15
282 additional compounds induced at least 15-fold increases. These compounds included several
283 frequently used control LRAs including (+)-JQ1, panobinostat, and vorinostat (Boehm et al., 2013;

284 Rasmussen et al., 2013). They also included several that have been previously reported to reverse
285 latency including AR-42, belinostat, bromosporine, CPI-203, dacinostat, I-BET-151, OTX015, PFI-1,
286 and resminostat (**Table 1**) (Mates et al., 2015; Rasmussen et al., 2013; Pan et al., 2017; Liang et al.,
287 2019; Shan et al., 2014; Li et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2017; Palmero et al., 2019). However,
288 we also identified three previously unreported LRAs including the HDAC inhibitor CUDC-101 (Cai et
289 al., 2010), which at 10 μ M induced an 18.7 ± 0.8 -fold increased fluorescence, the BET bromodomain
290 inhibitor molibresib (I-BET-762; 29.9 ± 2.5 -fold) (Nicodeme et al., 2010), and the HDAC inhibitor
291 quisinostat (JNJ-26481585; 50.3 ± 0.8 -fold) (Deleu et al., 2019; **Table 1**). CUDC-101, molibresib, and
292 quisinostat also maintained latency reversal with dose-dependence in both microplate reader and
293 flow cytometry-based methods (**Figures 5B-C**), while no major changes in cell viability were
294 observed except at the highest concentration of CUDC101 (70 μ M), where viability was reduced by
295 $51.5 \pm 8.1\%$ relative to untreated cells (**Figure 5C**). We also continued to see good correlation of the
296 two detection methods for cells treated with CUDC-101 ($r^2 = 0.38$, $p = 0.005$), molibresib ($r^2 = 0.57$, p
297 $= 0.0003$), and quisinostat ($r^2 = 0.35$, $p = 0.007$; **Figures 5D-F**). Taken together, these results indicate
298 that the microplate reader-based method can successfully identify and validate dose-response
299 profiles of novel LRAs.

300

301 **4. Conclusion**

302 Here we demonstrate the ability to identify and characterize novel LRAs in high-throughput
303 format using J-Lat CD4+ T-cells and a standard microplate reader. The assay detects control LRAs
304 with dose dependence, along with significant correlations to results obtained from flow cytometry
305 using both the highly responsive J-Lat 10.6 cell line and poorly responsive J-Lat 6.3 cells. We further
306 demonstrate that this assay can be used to screen chemical libraries to identify novel LRAs, for
307 example CUDC-101, molibresib, and quisinostat. While other assays that detect viral proteins by

308 ELISA or measure reverse transcriptase activity are accessible to resource-limited laboratories,
309 these assays frequently require more processing steps and higher cost, particularly when used in
310 high-throughput contexts. In contrast, limitations of the microplate reader-based method describe
311 here include that auto-fluorescent compounds would be expected to appear as false positives,
312 although these could be ruled out by subsequently incubating compounds with Jurkat cells which
313 lack GFP fluorescence. Further, as J-Lat cells represent an *in vitro* model of HIV latency, new LRA
314 hits will still require further validation such as measures of RNA induction or viral replication capacity
315 after reactivation in primary CD4+ cells from study participants living with HIV. Nevertheless, this
316 approach affords *in vitro*-based research on known and novel LRAs and mechanisms of HIV latency
317 without the need for flow cytometry, thereby providing additional access to discovery-stage HIV cure
318 research for highly resource-constrained laboratories in the absence of flow cytometry
319 infrastructure and expertise.

320

321 **5. Abbreviations**

322 ART, antiretroviral therapy; CC₅₀, half-maximal cytotoxic concentration; HDAC, histone deacetylase;
323 LRA, latency-reversing agent; MTT, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide
324 tetrazolium.

325

326 **6. Author contributions**

327 C.E.N.: Investigation, laboratory analysis, drafting of the original manuscript. U.S.:
328 Investigation, laboratory analysis, drafting of the original manuscript. K.L.: Investigation, laboratory
329 analysis. J.C.: Investigation, laboratory analysis. J.M.S.: Supervision, review & editing. L.J.M.: Funding
330 acquisition, review & editing. R.N.N.: Supervision, review & editing. S.N.E.: Supervision. F.N.K.:

331 Funding acquisition, supervision, writing, review & editing. I.T.: Funding acquisition,
332 conceptualization, supervision, writing, review & editing.

333

334 **7. Funding sources**

335 Funding was provided by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation through the Calestous Juma
336 Science Leadership Fellowship from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation awarded to Fidele Ntie-
337 Kang (grant award number: INV-036848). FNK also acknowledges joint funding from the Bill &
338 Melinda Gates Foundation (award number: INV-055897) and LifeArc (Grant ID: 10646) under the
339 African Drug Discovery Accelerator program. Further funding is acknowledged from the Alexander
340 von Humboldt Foundation, Bonn Germany through the Research Group Linkage program. This work
341 was also supported by the following grants to L.J.M.: Beyond Antiretroviral Treatment (BEAT)-HIV
342 Delaney Collaboratory Grant UM1 AI164570, by the Robert I. Jacobs Fund of the Philadelphia
343 Foundation, the Penn Center for AIDS Research Grant P30 AI 045008, and the Herbert Kean, M.D.,
344 Family Professorship. I.T. was supported by a Project Grant from the Canadian Institutes for Health
345 Research (CIHR PJT-153057).

346

347 **8. References**

348 Abdel-Mohsen M, Chavez L, Tandon R, Chew GM, Deng X, Danesh A, Keating S, Lanteri M, Samuels
349 ML, Hoh R, Sacha JB, Norris PJ, Niki T, Shikuma CM, Hirashima M, Deeks SG, Ndhlovu LC, Pillai SK.
350 Human Galectin-9 Is a Potent Mediator of HIV Transcription and Reactivation. PLoS Pathog. 2016
351 2;12(6):e1005677. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1005677.

352

353 Abner E, Stoszko M, Zeng L, Chen HC, Izquierdo-Bouldstridge A, Konuma T, Zorita E, Fanunza E,
354 Zhang Q, Mahmoudi T, Zhou MM, Filion GJ, Jordan A. A New Quinoline BRD4 Inhibitor Targets a

355 Distinct Latent HIV-1 Reservoir for Reactivation from Other "Shock" Drugs. *J Virol.* 2018
356 27;92(10):e02056-17. doi: 10.1128/JVI.02056-17.

357
358 Acchioni C, Remoli AL, Marsili G, Acchioni M, Nardolillo I, Orsatti R, Farcomeni S, Palermo E, Perrotti
359 E, Barreca ML, Sabatini S, Sandini S, Parolin C, Lin R, Borsetti A, Hiscott J, Sgarbanti M. Alternate NF-
360 κ B-Independent Signaling Reactivation of Latent HIV-1 Provirus. *J Virol.* 2019 Aug 28;93(18):e00495-
361 19. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00495-19.

362
363 Andersen RJ, Ntie-Kang F, Tietjen I. Natural product-derived compounds in HIV suppression,
364 remission, and eradication strategies. *Antiviral Res.* 2018 Oct;158:63-77. doi:
365 10.1016/j.antiviral.2018.07.016.

366
367 Board NL, Moskovljevic M, Wu F, Siliciano RF, Siliciano JD. Engaging innate immunity in HIV-1 cure
368 strategies. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2022 Aug;22(8):499-512. doi: 10.1038/s41577-021-00649-1.

369
370 Boehm D, Calvanese V, Dar RD, Xing S, Schroeder S, Martins L, Aull K, Li PC, Planelles V, Bradner JE,
371 Zhou MM, Siliciano RF, Weinberger L, Verdin E, Ott M. BET bromodomain-targeting compounds
372 reactivate HIV from latency via a Tat-independent mechanism. *Cell Cycle.* 2013 Feb 1;12(3):452-62.
373 doi: 10.4161/cc.23309.

374
375 Cai X, Zhai HX, Wang J, Forrester J, Qu H, Yin L, Lai CJ, Bao R, Qian C. Discovery of 7-(4-(3-
376 ethynylphenylamino)-7-methoxyquinazolin-6-yloxy)-N-hydroxyheptanamide (CUDc-101) as a
377 potent multi-acting HDAC, EGFR, and HER2 inhibitor for the treatment of cancer. *J Med Chem.* 2010
378 Mar 11;53(5):2000-9. doi: 10.1021/jm901453q.

379

380 Deleu S, Lemaire M, Arts J, Menu E, Van Valckenborgh E, King P, Broek IV, De Raeve H, Van Camp B,
381 Croucher P, Vanderkerken K. The effects of JNJ-26481585, a novel hydroxamate-based histone
382 deacetylase inhibitor, on the development of multiple myeloma in the 5T2MM and 5T33MM murine
383 models. *Leukemia*. 2009 Oct;23(10):1894-903. doi: 10.1038/leu.2009.121.

384

385 Hashemi P, Barreto K, Bernhard W, Lomness A, Honson N, Pfeifer TA, Harrigan PR, Sadowski I.
386 Compounds producing an effective combinatorial regimen for disruption of HIV-1 latency. *EMBO Mol*
387 *Med*. 2018 Feb;10(2):160-174. doi: 10.15252/emmm.201708193.

388

389 Hsieh E, Janssens DH, Paddison PJ, Browne EP, Henikoff S, OhAinle M, Emerman M. A modular
390 CRISPR screen identifies individual and combination pathways contributing to HIV-1 latency. *PLoS*
391 *Pathog*. 2023 Jan 27;19(1):e1011101. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1011101.

392

393 Fernandez G, Zeichner SL. Cell line-dependent variability in HIV activation employing DNMT
394 inhibitors. *Virology*. 2010 Oct 13;7:266. doi: 10.1186/1743-422X-7-266.

395

396 Jordan A, Bisgrove D, Verdin E. HIV reproducibly establishes a latent infection after acute infection
397 of T cells in vitro. *EMBO J*. 2003 Apr 15;22(8):1868-77. doi: 10.1093/emboj/cdg188.

398

399 Li G, Zhang Z, Reszka-Blanco N, Li F, Chi L, Ma J, Jeffrey J, Cheng L, Su L. Specific Activation In Vivo
400 of HIV-1 by a Bromodomain Inhibitor from Monocytic Cells in Humanized Mice under Antiretroviral
401 Therapy. *J Virol*. 2019 May 29;93(12):e00233-19. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00233-19.

402

403 Liang T, Zhang X, Lai F, Lin J, Zhou C, Xu X, Tan X, Liu S, Li L. A novel bromodomain inhibitor, CPI-203,
404 serves as an HIV-1 latency-reversing agent by activating positive transcription elongation factor b.
405 *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2019 Jun;164:237-251. doi: 10.1016/j.bcp.2019.04.005.

406
407 Lu P, Qu X, Shen Y, Jiang Z, Wang P, Zeng H, Ji H, Deng J, Yang X, Li X, Lu H, Zhu H. The BET inhibitor
408 OTX015 reactivates latent HIV-1 through P-TEFb. *Sci Rep.* 2016 Apr 12;6:24100. doi:
409 10.1038/srep24100.

410
411 Lu P, Shen Y, Yang H, Wang Y, Jiang Z, Yang X, Zhong Y, Pan H, Xu J, Lu H, Zhu H. BET inhibitors RVX-
412 208 and PFI-1 reactivate HIV-1 from latency. *Sci Rep.* 2017 Nov 30;7(1):16646. doi: 10.1038/s41598-
413 017-16816-1.

414
415 Mates JM, de Silva S, Lustberg M, Van Deusen K, Baiocchi RA, Wu L, Kwiek JJ. A Novel Histone
416 Deacetylase Inhibitor, AR-42, Reactivates HIV-1 from Chronically and Latently Infected CD4+ T-cells
417 *Retrovirology.* 2015;7:1-5. doi: 10.4137/RRT.S31632.

418
419 Matsuda K, Kobayakawa T, Tsuchiya K, Hattori SI, Nomura W, Gatanaga H, Yoshimura K, Oka S, Endo
420 Y, Tamamura H, Mitsuya H, Maeda K. Benzolactam-related compounds promote apoptosis of HIV-
421 infected human cells via protein kinase C-induced HIV latency reversal. *J Biol Chem.* 2019 Jan
422 4;294(1):116-129. doi: 10.1074/jbc.RA118.005798.

423
424 Mbonye U, Karn J. The cell biology of HIV-1 latency and rebound. *Retrovirology.* 2024 Apr 5;21(1):6.
425 doi: 10.1186/s12977-024-00639-w.

426

427 Nichols Doyle R, Yang V, Damoiseaux R, Fregoso OI. NSC95397 is a Novel HIV Latency Reversing
428 Agent. *bioRxiv*. 2023 May 25:2023.05.24.542213. doi: 10.1101/2023.05.24.542213.

429

430 Nicodeme E, Jeffrey KL, Schaefer U, Beinke S, Dewell S, Chung CW, Chandwani R, Marazzi I, Wilson
431 P, Coste H, White J, Kirilovsky J, Rice CM, Lora JM, Prinjha RK, Lee K, Tarakhovsky A. Suppression of
432 inflammation by a synthetic histone mimic. *Nature*. 2010 Dec 23;468(7327):1119-23. doi:
433 10.1038/nature09589.

434

435 Palermo E, Acchioni C, Di Carlo D, Zevini A, Muscolini M, Ferrari M, Castiello L, Virtuoso S, Borsetti
436 A, Antonelli G, Turriziani O, Sgarbanti M, Hiscott J. Activation of Latent HIV-1 T Cell Reservoirs with a
437 Combination of Innate Immune and Epigenetic Regulators. *J Virol*. 2019 Oct 15;93(21):e01194-19.
438 doi: 10.1128/JVI.01194-19.

439

440 Pan H, Lu P, Shen Y, Wang Y, Jiang Z, Yang X, Zhong Y, Yang H, Khan IU, Zhou M, Li B, Zhang Z, Xu J,
441 Lu H, Zhu H. The bromodomain and extraterminal domain inhibitor bromosporine synergistically
442 reactivates latent HIV-1 in latently infected cells. *Oncotarget*. 2017 Oct 6;8(55):94104-94116. doi:
443 10.18632/oncotarget.21585.

444

445 Rasmussen TA, Søgaaard OS, Brinkmann C, Wightman F, Lewin SR, Melchjorsen J, Dinarello C,
446 Østergaard L, Tolstrup M. Comparison of HDAC inhibitors in clinical development: effect on HIV
447 production in latently infected cells and T-cell activation. *Hum Vaccin Immunother*. 2013
448 May;9(5):993-1001. doi: 10.4161/hv.23800.

449

450 Richard K, Williams DE, de Silva ED, Brockman MA, Brumme ZL, Andersen RJ, Tietjen I. Identification
451 of Novel HIV-1 Latency-Reversing Agents from a Library of Marine Natural Products. *Viruses*. 2018
452 Jun 27;10(7):348. doi: 10.3390/v10070348.

453

454 Shan L, Xing S, Yang HC, Zhang H, Margolick JB, Siliciano RF. Unique characteristics of histone
455 deacetylase inhibitors in reactivation of latent HIV-1 in Bcl-2-transduced primary resting CD4+ T
456 cells. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 2014 Jan;69(1):28-33. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkt338.

457

458 Van Schalkwyk C, Mahy M, Johnson LF, Imai-Eaton JW. Updated Data and Methods for the 2023
459 UNAIDS HIV Estimates. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr*. 2024 Jan 1;95(1S):e1-e4. doi:
460 10.1097/QAI.0000000000003344.

461

462 **Figure captions**

463

464 **Figure 1.** Flowchart of microplate reader-based method using J-Lat cells.

465

466 **Figure 2.** Activity of prostratin and romidepsin in J-Lat 10.6 cells as measured by the microplate
467 reader-based method (**A-C**). Panels **D-F** show viability of the same cells from the microplate reader-
468 based method. **G-I**, representative flow cytometry data from J-Lat cells treated with 0.1% DMSO
469 vehicle control (**G**), 1 μ M prostratin (**H**) or 0.1 μ M romidepsin (**I**). For each example, the right-hand
470 box and values denote gating and percent GFP-positive cells, respectively. **J-L**, Percent GFP-positive
471 cells from **A-F** as detected by flow cytometry. In columns, **A**, **D**, and **J** are results for J-Lat cells
472 cultured for 24 hours at 1 million cells/mL, **B**, **E**, **K** show cultures at 2.5 million cells/mL, and **C**, **F**, **L**
473 show cultures at 5.0 million cells/mL. All data are presented as the mean \pm s.e.m. from four
474 independent experiments.

475

476 **Figure 3.** Comparisons of LRA-induced GFP detection using the microplate reader-based method
477 and flow cytometry. Panels **A-C** show correlations of all data points in **Figure 2** across four
478 independent experiments for prostratin and romidepsin with microplate reader data graphed on the
479 y-axis (indicating fold-change in GFP expression over untreated cells) and flow cytometry data on the
480 x-axis (indicating percent GFP-positive cells in live cell gate). Panels **A-C** show results from all
481 experiments with 1 million cells/mL, 2.5 million cells/mL, and 5 million cells/mL, respectively. For
482 panel **C**, individual data for prostratin (**D**) and romidepsin (**E**) are shown. *, linear regression p-value
483 < 0.001.

484

485 **Figure 4.** Activity of prostratin and romidepsin in J-Lat 6.3 cells as measured by the microplate
486 reader-based method (**A**) and flow cytometry (**B**). Panel **C** shows correlations of data points with
487 microplate reader data graphed on the y-axis (indicating fold-change in GFP expression over
488 untreated cells) and flow cytometry data on the x-axis (indicating percent GFP-positive cells in live
489 gate). Panel **D** shows viability of cells from the microplate reader-based method in **A**. All data are
490 presented as the mean \pm s.e.m. from three independent experiments except panel **C** which reflects
491 data from two independent experiments. *, linear regression p-value = 0.005.

492

493 **Figure 5.** Discovery of novel LRAs from an epigenetic compound library. **A**, Correlations of
494 microplate reader and flow cytometry data for 79 epigenetic modifiers screened at 10 μ M. The blue
495 dot denotes prostratin positive control, and other dots with colors denote 3 compounds that induce
496 GFP expression at least 15-fold over untreated cells in the microplate reader-based method that
497 have not been reported as LRAs. Data are presented as the average of duplicates obtained by
498 microplate reader method and flow cytometry. *, linear regression p-value < 0.001. **B-C**, Dose
499 response profiles of latency reversal due to molibresib, quisinostat, and CUDC-101 using the
500 microplate reader-based method (**B**) and flow cytometry (**C**). Data are presented as the mean \pm
501 s.e.m. from four independent experiments. **D**, Viability of cells measured using microplate reader.
502 Data are presented as the mean \pm SD from two independent experiments. **E-G** Comparisons of LRA-
503 induced GFP detection using the microplate reader-based method and flow cytometry for CUDC-
504 101 (**E**), molibresib (**F**), and quisinostat (**G**). *, p values = 0.005, < 0.001, and 0.007, respectively.

505 **Table 1.** Latency reversal properties of epigenetic compounds assessed by microplate reader and
506 flow cytometry. LRAs that induce at least 15-fold GFP increase over untreated cells are underlined,
507 while colors denote previously unreported LRAs.

Compound	Microplate reader	Flow cytometry
	GFP fluorescence, relative to no-drug control	Percent HIV latency reversal (GFP+ cells)
4SC-202	0.3 ± 5.4	2.5 ± 3.5
A-366	0.6 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 2.0
Amodiaquine	6.9 ± 0.7	3.0 ± 1.2
Anacardic Acid	2.7 ± 0.3	1.9 ± 0.4
Apabetalone (RVX-208)	9.1 ± 1.5	4.8 ± 1.6
<u>AR-42</u>	<u>35.2 ± 3.3</u>	<u>59.6 ± 30.3</u>
AS-8351	1.7 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 2.7
<u>Belinostat (PXD101)</u>	<u>40.4 ± 0.5</u>	<u>52.5 ± 20.2</u>
BRD4770	9.8 ± 1.5	2.0 ± 0.7
<u>Bromosporine</u>	<u>78.5 ± 6.8</u>	<u>35.2 ± 2.3</u>
C646	0.5 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 2.0
CAY10602	0.0 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.1
CPI-169	0.4 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.5
<u>CPI-203</u>	<u>34.3 ± 3.9</u>	<u>21.8 ± 1.1</u>
CPI-360	12.0 ± 1.7	1.1 ± 1.6
CUDC-101	18.7 ± 0.8	49.4 ± 27.4
Curcumin	6.8 ± 1.0	19.5 ± 17.0
<u>Dacinostat (LAQ824)</u>	<u>75.5 ± 0.5</u>	<u>60.0 ± 21.3</u>
Daminozide	12.7 ± 2.0	1.2 ± 0.8
Decitabine	3.5 ± 0.5	1.9 ± 0.6
EI1	2.7 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.3
Entinostat (MS-275)	3.5 ± 0.0	8.0 ± 2.2
EPZ004777	3.0 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 1.7
EPZ015666 (GSK3235025)	2.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.2
EPZ020411	1.8 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.8
Fisetin	2.0 ± 0.2	9.9 ± 12.8
GSK 5959	10.1 ± 1.5	2.3 ± 0.1
GSK J1	0.0 ± 0.4	2.9 ± 0.9
GSK J4	2.9 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 3.7
GSK2801	6.6 ± 1.1	3.6 ± 3.1
GSK503	7.4 ± 1.1	3.3 ± 2.0
<u>I-BET151 (GSK1210151A)</u>	<u>45.6 ± 4.1</u>	<u>26.5 ± 6.2</u>
IOX1	2.8 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.0
JIB-04	0.0 ± 0.9	26.3 ± 11.5
<u>(+)-JQ1</u>	<u>57.8 ± 5.4</u>	<u>21.0 ± 2.5</u>
MI-136	5.6 ± 0.8	2.7 ± 0.4
MI-2 (Menin-MLL Inhibitor)	0.0 ± 2.8	3.0 ± 0.3
MI-463	3.0 ± 0.3	3.5 ± 1.3

ML324	3.2 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 2.6
MM-102	1.9 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.4
Mocetinostat (MGCD0103)	10.1 ± 0.8	13.7 ± 11.3
Molibresib (I-BET-762)	29.9 ± 2.5	17.0 ± 2.0
MS436	14.5 ± 1.7	16.6 ± 3.5
OF-1	12.0 ± 1.7	4.1 ± 1.7
OG-L002	4.2 ± 0.6	2.3 ± 0.1
ORY-1001 (RG-6016)	2.7 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.8
<u>OTX015</u>	<u>44.4 ± 4.8</u>	<u>19.5 ± 12.0</u>
<u>Panobinostat (LBH589)</u>	<u>63.8 ± 0.6</u>	<u>71.6 ± 40.2</u>
PCI-34051	0.3 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 1.5
<u>PFI-1 (PF-6405761)</u>	<u>33.2 ± 3.3</u>	<u>16.4 ± 1.2</u>
PFI-2	0.0 ± 0.3	16.4 ± 1.2
PFI-3	0.0 ± 0.3	4.6 ± 4.3
<u>Prostratin</u>	<u>41.7 ± 0.6</u>	<u>58.5 ± 3.5</u>
Quercetin	3.4 ± 0.5	7.7 ± 5.1
Quisinostat (JNJ-26481585)	50.3 ± 0.8	67.3 ± 9.3
Remodelin	1.2 ± 0.0	1.3 ± 1.9
<u>Resminostat</u>	<u>37.8 ± 1.2</u>	<u>38.1 ± 14.4</u>
RG108	0.0 ± 1.2	1.7 ± 2.4
RG2833 (RGFP109)	1.9 ± 0.2	5.1 ± 2.3
RGFP966	0.0 ± 0.2	6.4 ± 3.1
Salvianolic acid B	14.3 ± 1.2	3.0 ± 0.5
Selisistat (EX 527)	3.0 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.2
SGC 0946	2.7 ± 0.2	5.4 ± 2.4
SGC-CBP30	14.8 ± 1.4	2.5 ± 3.5
SGI-1027	3.0 ± 0.4	8.4 ± 11.8
SMI-16a	7.4 ± 1.2	4.4 ± 0.5
Splitomicin	2.8 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.6
SRT1720	4.5 ± 0.7	3.1 ± 0.9
Suberohydroxamic acid	9.3 ± 1.3	6.0 ± 0.2
Tacedinaline (CI994)	2.1 ± 0.0	5.2 ± 0.9
Thioguanine	0.0 ± 0.6	2.9 ± 2.6
TMP269	5.1 ± 0.7	3.4 ± 2.1
Tubastatin A	2.7 ± 0.4	3.3 ± 1.0
UNC0379	0.0 ± 1.0	3.2 ± 1.5
UNC0642	0.0 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.1
UNC1215	5.4 ± 0.9	2.2 ± 1.6
UNC1999	9.7 ± 1.5	1.4 ± 0.5
Valproic acid	12.4 ± 1.4	1.2 ± 1.7
<u>Vorinostat (SAHA, MK0683)</u>	<u>42.9 ± 2.9</u>	<u>34.6 ± 48.9</u>
Zebularine	7.6 ± 1.2	2.7 ± 0.1

GFP fluorescence in J-Lat 6.3 cells

A J-Lat 10.6 cells; 5M cells/mL

